

Online Educational Resources Library

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Nutrihealth and Wellness

TITLE	LINK	TYPE OF RESOURCE	AUTORSHIP	LICENCE	LANGUAGE
How your digestive system works - Emma Bryce	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Og5xAdC8EUI	Video	created by others	Creative Commons	English
Wearables and AI will be The Game Changer in Healthcare	https://digitalsalutem.com/wearables-and-ai-in-healthcare/	Other	created by others	Copyright	English
Peristalsis	https://media.istockphoto.com/id/1334784362/vector/peristalsis-as-anatomical-food-swallow-process-explanation-outline-diagram.jpg?s=612x612&w=0&k=20&c=BGcrbex1OIDNHVI26ZQ5dNYHFdQ_b0CCETpBQXMaaQ=	Image	created by others	Other	English
Global Food Crisis Finding Solutions with the Global Food and Nutrition Security Dashboard	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UC8-vRSFPIs	Video	created by others	Other	English
What Is BMR (Basal Metabolic Rate)?	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2r473DgCjI	Video	created by others	Copyright	English
What is digestion?	https://i0.wp.com/post.medicalnewstoday.com/wp-content/uploads/sites/3/2022/06/1958689-Digestion_1296x1296-body-1-1024x1024.png?w=1155&h=2723	Image	created by others	Other	English
Anatomy and Physiology of the Large Intestine	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=r3GVrCOSBTo	Video	created by others	Other	English
Anatomy and Physiology of the Stomach	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=GWARcInGAYs	Video	created by others	Other	English
Digestive System	https://i0.wp.com/post.medicalnewstoday.com/wp-	Image	created by others	Other	English

	content/uploads/sites/3/2022/06/1958689-Digestion_1296x1296-body-1-1024x1024.png?w=1155&h=2723				
Anatomy and Physiology of the Large Intestine, Animation	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=a0yGDipKWlo	Video	created by others	Other	English
Digestive System: Ingestion to Egestion Explained in Simple Words	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HW1_0LSJlwc	Video	created by others	Other	English
Best Nutrition Tracking Apps For Nutrition Coaches (MyFitnessPal Alternatives)	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=V3BLuyHoZuA	Video	created by others	Other	English
Nutrition tracking app	https://www.foodnoms.com/_next/static/media/hero.24cd529c.png	Image	created by others	Other	English
Wearables and AI article	https://digitalsalutem.com/wearables-and-ai-in-healthcare/	Other	created by others	Other	English
Top Wearable Medical Devices Used in Healthcare	https://healthnews.com/family-health/healthy-living/wearable-medical-devices-used-in-healthcare/	Other	created by others	Other	English
How effective is wearable health tech?	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=CyCdHV822Vo	Video	created by others	Other	English
Endoscopy - Upper GI Surgery PreOp® Patient Education	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=W1faSbFuLI8	Video	created by others	Other	English
Gastrointestinal endoscopy: an option to assess or monitor digestive diseases	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LW623g59htw	Video	created by others	Other	English
Endoscopy	https://www.hopkinsmedicine.org/-/media/images/health/2_-treatment/gastroenterology/endoscopic-procedure-illustration.png?h=400&iar=0&mh=400&mw=670&w=582&hash=2AB34F34481652BF9F6C6798B4F749C7	Image	created by others	Other	English

What is peristalsis?	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=kVjeNZA5pi4	Video	created by others	Other	English
Nutrition and art ideas	https://www.pinterest.com/lackey1040/nutrition-and-art/	Visual presentation	created by others	Other	English
5 Food Photography Tips: Food Styling, Photography Lighting, and More	https://www.youtube.com/watch?app=desktop&v=vKaNQ4af-6w	Video	created by others	Other	English
6 Food Photography Tricks In 2 Minutes!!	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=A6vr0hg3OUE	Video	created by others	Other	English
https://profoto.com/de/tips/food-photography-with-smartphone	https://profoto.com/de/tips/food-photography-with-smartphone	Other	created by others	Other	English
A healthy diet, a healthier world	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=XMcab1MFaLc	Video	created by others	Other	English
Global Food Crisis Finding Solutions with the Global Food and Nutrition Security Dashboard	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UC8-vRSFPIs	Video	created by others	Other	English
https://globalnutritionreport.org/resources/about-malnutrition/	https://globalnutritionreport.org/resources/about-malnutrition/	Other	created by others	Other	English
How to Calculate Your Calorie Needs (Beginner's Guide)	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ynxONrguhQ0	Video	created by others	Other	English
https://www.britannica.com/video/143178/Most-process-intestine-system-channels-water-nutrients	https://www.britannica.com/video/143178/Most-process-intestine-system-channels-water-nutrients	Other	created by others	Other	English
https://furtherwithfood.org/resources/grocery-budget-calculator/	https://furtherwithfood.org/resources/grocery-budget-calculator/	Interactive resource	created by others	Other	English
HOW TO MAKE A GROCERY LIST FAST	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=oIV39A-u6VY	Video	created by others	Other	English
Human and Mammal intestine	https://www.researchgate.net/publication/366555401/figure/fig1/AS:11431281109482898@1672032607406/Abdominal-	Image	created by others	Other	English

	anatomy-of-intestinal-tracts-between-humans-A-and-adult-zebrafish-B.png				
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OrganKits
for STEAM

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DISCOVER-IN
anatomy at your hands

